
AI Governance around the world

Country Profile: China

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About The Alan Turing Institute

The Alan Turing Institute is the UK's national institute for data science and artificial intelligence.

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About the project

Introduction

The international AI governance landscape continues to evolve as jurisdictions around the world balance the need to navigate increased competition with earlier commitments to advancing international alignment and cooperation on AI governance and safety. Many jurisdictions have recognised the strategic implications of AI, both for economic prosperity and national security, and accelerated investment in domestic AI infrastructure has begun to engender a more competitive international environment. However, the role of international trade and global cooperation remains crucial in realising the economic benefits of AI while effectively managing the technology's risks.

As high-level AI principles are translated into concrete policies and distinct regulatory frameworks, jurisdictions are managing the tensions between competitive and cooperative priorities. Meaningful progress towards effective international AI governance will require a clear and detailed understanding of how different countries are approaching AI governance in practice. Tracking primary source policy initiatives over the past decade, the *AI governance around the world* project sheds light on shifting national priorities on AI, dynamics of cooperation and competition, and potential areas of international alignment.

Project aims

The *AI governance around the world* project seeks to map this evolving landscape through a series of country profiles based on a consistent framework. Each profile provides a descriptive overview of a jurisdiction's approach to AI regulation and standardisation, highlighting the high-level aims and principles, definitions of relevant technologies, key policy initiatives and the main features of the respective standardisation systems. Drawing exclusively on primary sources, the country profiles analyse legal and policy instruments, national strategies, standardisation initiatives, and

public investments that reflect the varied and evolving approaches that different jurisdictions are taking to AI governance.

This series offers a foundation for comparative analysis and future work on global regulatory interoperability without commenting on the efficacy of the specific governance models being adopted at the jurisdictional level. As more profiles are developed, the project aims to contribute to international understanding of where alignment is emerging and where deeper coordination may be needed.

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Executive summary

China has emerged as one of the largest AI economies in the world and an early mover in AI regulation. Aiming to secure the status of global leader in AI innovation by 2030, the Chinese government is developing a comprehensive regulatory framework drawing on input from industry and academia. Its strategy seeks to balance the rapid promotion of AI development with structured oversight, aiming to foster societal integration while proactively managing inherent risks. More specifically, the government has chosen to create and enforce strict rules for high-risk AI applications—such as anthropomorphic interactive AI services, recommendation algorithms, and the use of ‘deep synthesis technologies’ in internet services—while allowing the private sector to drive development and adoption in less critical areas.

The Chinese administration is equally active in AI standardisation. The national standard development system is centrally coordinated by the Standardisation Administration of China (SAC) and is organised hierarchically across territorial levels. Existing AI standards cover both cross-sectoral and sector-specific issues, and State authorities see engagement in international AI standardisation as an opportunity to bolster the international competitiveness of the Chinese economy.

Timeline

Jul 2017

New Generation AI Development Plan

National AI Strategy

Jun 2019

Responsible AI Governance Principles

Non-binding ethical guidelines emphasising fairness, transparency, privacy, and human oversight in AI development

Oct 2021

New Generation AI Ethical Norms

Non-binding guidelines extending ethical AI governance into the full lifecycle of development, supply, and use

Mar 2022

Provisions on Algorithmic Recommendations in Internet Services

Regulation governing algorithmic recommendation systems on internet platforms, requiring transparency and user controls.

Jan 2023

Provisions on Deep Synthesis Internet Information Services

Regulation governing the creation and distribution of deepfake and AI-generated synthetic media, requiring providers to label content and obtain user consent

Aug 2023

Interim Measures for Generative AI Services

Regulation governing generative AI services, requiring security assessments and ensuring generated content aligns with core values

Mar 2025

AI-Generated Content Labelling Measures

Implementing measures requiring platforms and AI providers to label AI-generated or synthetic content across text, image, audio, and video.

Jul 2026

Interim Measures for AI Anthropomorphic Interaction Services

Implementing measures requiring platforms and AI providers to label AI-generated or synthetic content across text, image, audio, and video.

Regulatory Approach to AI

High-level aims and principles¹

Since 2017, when the Chinese government published its first national AI strategy—the *New Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan (AIDP)*²—AI has remained a key strategic priority for the administration. Positioning AI as the engine that will drive China’s next economic development cycle, the AIDP established three-step roadmap with time-bound milestones: by 2020, AI development and deployment would match globally advanced levels and the national AI industry would become a real driver of economic growth; by 2025, the Chinese research ecosystem would achieve major breakthroughs in basic AI theory and AI would become the major driving force of for China’s industrial development; finally, by 2030, China aspires to become the most advanced AI innovation centre in the world. arca

To meet these targets, the AIDP proposes an integrated approach whereby the government would invest across AI R&D, commercial applications, and industrial policy to pursue 6 overarching goals:

- Building an open and collaborative AI innovation system.
- Fostering a high-end and efficient intelligent economy.
- Constructing a safe and effective intelligent society.
- Strengthening civil-military integration in AI.
- Developing ubiquitous and efficient intelligent infrastructure.
- Making forward-looking arrangements for major next-generation AI science and technology projects.

¹ When evaluating Chinese government’s approach to ethics, it is important to consider that concepts such as ‘legal’, ‘ethical’, ‘safety’, or ‘privacy’ may carry different semantic connotations compared to their use in Western policy or academic discourse.

² State Council of the People’s Republic of China, [New Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan](#) (新一代人工智能发展规划), 2017.

Importantly, the Plan recognised that AI development requires a clear governance framework to support investments, and called for the formulation of AI laws, regulations, and ethical norms; establishing technical standards and IP protection schemes; creating evaluation and oversight mechanisms for AI safety; implementing workforce training programmes and promoting AI literacy across society.

Following the publication of the AIDP, the National New Generation AI Governance Expert Committee³ issued the *Governance Principles for a new generation of AI* (2019). The principles emphasised that AI development should prioritise “enhancing the common well-being of humanity” as well as “safeguarding societal security and respecting human rights”.⁴ Specific guiding principles highlighted in the document include:

- Harmony and friendliness.
- Fairness.
- Inclusiveness.
- Privacy.
- Safety.
- Shared responsibility.
- Open cooperation.
- Agile governance.

The same Committee published the *Ethical Norms for New Generation Artificial Intelligence* in 2021,⁵ providing more practical guidance for regulators, developers, providers and users of AI systems ahead of the foreseen introduction of binding rules.

³ An expert committee established by the Ministry of Science and Technology (MOST) to research policy recommendations for AI governance and identify areas for international cooperation. The Committee’s members are leading experts from both industry and academia.

⁴ National New Generation Artificial Intelligence Governance Expert Committee, [Governance Principles for a New Generation of AI \(English Translation\)](#) 《新一代人工智能治理原则——发展负责任的人工智能》, 2019.

⁵ National New Generation Artificial Intelligence Governance Expert Committee, [Ethical Norms for New Generation Artificial Intelligence \(English Translation\)](#) 《新一代人工智能伦理规范》, 2021.

The guidance specified how ethical principles can be applied across the AI development and deployment cycle. Key principles highlighted in this policy are:

- Advancing human welfare.
- Fairness and justice.
- Privacy.
- Security.
- Accountability.
- Assuring the controllability and trustworthiness of AI systems.

In October 2023, the Chinese government published the *Global AI Governance Initiative*, laying out its vision for international AI governance.⁶ The initiative calls for global cooperation around AI safety, respect for national sovereignty, opposition to technological monopolies and to the misuse of AI, and greater representation for developing countries in multilateral policymaking processes. It positions AI governance as a shared global issue requiring multi-stakeholder participation and international standards, and mentions the option of centralised coordination under the United Nations framework.

In March 2024, the Chinese government introduced the 'AI Plus' initiative, a strategic ten-year roadmap designed to embed AI technologies across the national economy and society by 2035.⁷ This plan was further specified through a policy directive issued in August 2025, which established concrete deployment milestones. Specifically, the government targets a 70% penetration rate for AI-powered 'intelligent terminals' and autonomous agents within key industrial and public sectors by 2027. By 2030, the roadmap mandates the deployment of AI applications across 90% of the broader

⁶ Ministry of Foreign Affairs, [Global AI Governance Initiative](#) 《全球人工智能治理倡议》, 2023.

⁷ State Council of the People's Republic of China, [China releases full text of the Government Work Report](#), 2024.

economy, culminating in the comprehensive integration of AI into all facets of economic and social life by 2035.⁸

Taken together, the Chinese' government AI policy strategy has evolved from a model primarily focused on R&D investment and industrial capacity (2017–2019), through an ethical and governance framing phase establishing soft-law principles (2019–2023), toward a more integrated approach that simultaneously pursues broad economic deployment and increasingly specific regulatory oversight (2024–present). Throughout this evolution, the government has consistently positioned itself as both promoter and regulator of AI development—a dual role reflected in the recurrent emphasis on balancing 'development and security' (发展与安全).

Definitions of relevant technologies

Rather than establishing a single, comprehensive definition of AI, the Chinese government has only defined specific AI applications and algorithms within the context of individual regulatory instruments.

The 2022 *Provisions on the Management of Algorithmic Recommendations in Internet Information Services* define 'algorithmic recommendation technology' as “the use of generative or synthetic-type, personalized recommendation-type, ranking and selection-type, search filter-type, dispatching and decision-making-type, and other such algorithmic technologies to provide information to users”.⁹

Similarly, the 2023 *Provisions on the Administration of Deep Synthesis Internet Information Services* only define 'deep synthesis technology' as comprising “technologies using generative and synthesizing algorithms, with deep learning and

⁸ State Council of the People's Republic of China, [China issues guideline to accelerate 'AI Plus' integration across key sectors](#), 2025.

⁹ See p. 12.

virtual reality as representative examples, to produce text, images, sound, video, virtual settings, and other such information”.¹⁰

The 2023 *Interim Administrative Measures for Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) Services*, define ‘generative AI technologies’ as the “models and related technologies with the ability to generate text, pictures, audio, video and other content”.^{11 12 13}

Key Regulatory Initiatives

National Regulatory Initiatives

The AIDP established the administration's ambition to introduce initial AI laws and regulations by 2025, and to develop a comprehensive regulatory framework by 2030. To date, the administration has introduced four regulations targeting recommendation algorithms, ‘deep synthesis technologies’, generative AI services, and ‘anthropomorphic interactive AI services’. In August 2023, the State Council of China announced that it intends to draft a comprehensive AI Law and develop regulations governing government data-sharing and data security management.¹⁴ At the time of writing, these are still being developed.

¹⁰ See p. 12.

¹¹ See p. 13.

¹² Yet another targeted definition of an AI-related concept can be found in the State Administration for Market Regulation and Standardisation’s draft standard on *Security specification and assessment methods for machine learning algorithms*. Here, “machine learning algorithm[s]” are defined as “algorithms [that] use machine learning technologies and theories to solve problems. They clearly define a limited and ordered set of rules and generate classifications, reasoning, predictions, and other outputs based on input data”. Source: State Administration for Market Regulation, [Information Security Technology-Security Specification and Assessment Methods for Machine Learning Algorithms \(English Translation\)](#) 《信息安全技术 机器学习算法安全评估规范》, 2021.

¹³ It is worth mentioning also that the Standards Administration of China (SAC) proposed a general definition of AI in a 2018 White Paper on AI Standardisation: “In the view of this white paper, AI is the theories, technologies, methods, and application systems for using digital computers or digital computer-controlled machines to simulate, extend, and expand human intelligence, perceive environments and acquire knowledge, and use knowledge to obtain the best results”.

¹⁴ State Council of the People’s Republic of China, [Legislative Work Plan](#) 《国务院办公厅关于印发国务院2023年度立法工作计划的通知》, 2023.

Interestingly, the Chinese government has so far privileged application-specific regulations, introducing targeted rules for especially risky uses of AI technologies rather than adopting cross-cutting or industry-specific AI laws.

Provisions on the Management of Algorithmic Recommendations in Internet Information Services¹⁵

The *Provisions on the Management of Algorithmic Recommendations in Internet Information Services*, which entered into force on 1 March 2022, govern the use of recommendation algorithms in internet services in China.

Providers using these algorithms must register them in a public registry managed by the CAC, including details on the training datasets used and safety measures implemented. For services with the potential to ‘shape public opinion’ or ‘mobilise society’, providers are responsible for ensuring the security of their systems, carrying out formal risk assessments, and implementing monitoring procedures. Documentation of these assessments must be filed in the public registry. Furthermore, service providers are strictly prohibited from deploying algorithms that manipulate public opinion, engage in anti-competitive behaviour, exploit user vulnerabilities, or endanger national security. Providers of news information services need to obtain a specific license and need to ensure the truthfulness of the information generated by their systems. Finally, providers of internet information services must ensure that users can identify when they interact with an algorithm and offer them opt-out mechanisms.

Provisions on the Administration of Deep Synthesis Internet Information Services¹⁶

¹⁵ Cyberspace Administration of China, [Provisions on the Management of Algorithmic Recommendations in Internet Information Services](#) 《互联网信息服务算法推荐管理规定》, 2021.

¹⁶ Cyberspace Administration of China, [Provisions on the Administration of Deep Synthesis Internet Information Services](#) 《互联网信息服务深度合成管理规定》, 2022.

Entered into force in January 2023, the *Provisions on the Administration of Deep Synthesis Internet Information Services* apply to the use of deep synthesis technologies to provide internet information services.

The measures cover four main pillars—data security, transparency, content management and labelling, and technical security—and set obligations both for providers and users of deep synthesis information services. The main goal of the regulation is to prevent harm caused by deepfakes. Key requirements include enabling users to discern when they are interacting with synthetic content, having procedures in place to ensure the security of data and personal information, conducting identity verification of users, and establishing a database of characteristics that can be used to identify unlawful or harmful content.

Interim Administrative Measures for Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) Services¹⁷

Effective from August 2023, the *Interim Administrative Measures for Generative AI Services* set forth a diverse array of requirements for generative AI service providers. These include measures related to training datasets, tagging and labelling of AI-generated content, data protection protocols, and the protection of user rights.

Providers must establish a mechanism to receive and address complaints from users, including user requests for accessing, downloading, or deleting their personal information. They must remove 'illegal content' from their platforms and report incidents to the competent authorities. Generative AI services capable of having an impact on public opinion or social mobilisation must also undergo further security assessments and algorithm filing in accordance with the *Provisions on the Management of Algorithmic Recommendations in Internet Information Services*.

¹⁷ Cyberspace Administration of China, [Interim Measures for the Management of Generative Artificial Intelligence Services](#) 《生成式人工智能服务管理暂行办法》, 2023.

Measures for Labelling AI-Generated Synthetic Content¹⁸

The *Measures for Labelling AI-generated Synthetic Content* entered into force in March 2025 and created a mandatory labelling and provenance regime for AI-generated content.

They require service providers to ensure content generated by their AI systems is identifiable both through ‘explicit labels’ that are clearly perceptible to users and ‘implicit’ ones embedded into file data or metadata. The measures cover AI-generated text, images, audio, and video, and extend responsibility beyond AI generation providers to content-sharing platforms, app distribution platforms, and end users.

Interim Measures for the Administration of AI Anthropomorphic Interaction Services¹⁹

Effective from 15 July 2026, this regulation targets AI services that simulate human personality, communication styles, and continuous emotional interaction such as AI companionship, emotional care, and support systems.

The regulation addresses relational and psychological risks, including emotional dependence, addiction, manipulation, self-harm, and loss of autonomy through service design and risk management obligations. For example, providers must ensure their systems don’t generate content that can encourage self-harm or suicide, induce emotional dependence or addiction, damage users’ real interpersonal relationships, or induce unreasonable decisions through emotional manipulation. Providers must also ensure the privacy and the protection of personal information shared by users, embed risk warnings into the design of their systems, and provide guidance on preserving mental health and emotional boundaries in the use of their services. Importantly, they

¹⁸ Cyberspace Administration of China, [Measures for Labelling AI-Generated Synthetic Content](#) 《人工智能生成合成内容标识办法》, 2025.

¹⁹ Cyberspace Administration of China, [Interim Measures for the Administration of AI Anthropomorphic Interaction Services](#) 《人工智能拟人化互动服务管理暂行办法》, 2026.

are forbidden from designing systems whose objective is to replace social interactions, exercise psychological control, or induce emotional dependency.

Local Regulatory Initiatives

Chinese provincial and municipal governments have also begun implementing AI governance frameworks. Local initiatives don't always follow a consistent format: some, such as the Shanghai and Shenzhen measures, take the form of local regulations, while others, such as those adopted in Beijing²⁰, Hangzhou²¹ and Guangzhou²², are better understood as policy guidelines, action plans or implementation plans. In this section, we limit our focus to local regulations.

Shanghai Regulation on Promoting the Development of the AI Industry²³

Effective from October 2022, the *Shanghai Regulation on Promoting the Development of the AI Industry* propose a set of pro-innovation anticipatory regulation mechanisms, including AI sandboxes, the establishment of a municipal strategic advisory committee, public compute governance, industry engagement to co-design regulation, and the development of local standards. The regulation requires high-risk AI systems to align with the principles of “necessity, appropriateness and controllability”, while allowing more flexibility for developers and users trialling less critical applications.

²⁰ Beijing Municipal People's Government General Office, [Measures for Promoting the Innovative Development of General Artificial Intelligence in Beijing](#) 《北京市促进通用人工智能创新发展的若干措施》, 2023. The measures focus on computing power, data, models, application scenarios and an inclusive/prudent regulatory environment.

²¹ Hangzhou Municipal People's Government, [Implementation Plan for Accelerating the Construction of an Artificial Intelligence Innovation Highland in Hangzhou](#) 《杭州市加快建设人工智能创新高地实施方案》, 2025. The plan includes AI industrial monitoring, inclusive/prudent safety governance, observation and tolerance periods for new technologies and business models, and accelerated AI-related legislation.

²² Guangzhou Municipal People's Government General Office, [Implementation Plan for Promoting High-Quality Development of the Artificial Intelligence Industry in Guangzhou](#) 《广州市促进人工智能产业高质量发展实施方案》, 2026. The plan emphasises AI+ industry applications, vertical models, public scenario-opening and AI industrial-chain development.

²³ Shanghai Municipal People's Congress, [Regulations on Promoting the Development of the Artificial Intelligence Sector \(English Translation\)](#) 《上海市促进人工智能产业发展条例》, 2022.

Regulations on the Promotion of Artificial Intelligence Industry in the Shenzhen Special Economic Zone²⁴

Effective since 1 November 2022, the Shenzhen AI Regulations aim to stimulate the local AI sector by integrating public financial support with a flexible risk-management framework. Under this structure, AI services and products classified as low risk by the Shenzhen government can pursue testing and certification even in the absence of national or local standards, provided they meet international product standards or specifications. The regulations also require the municipal government to establish an AI Ethics Committee responsible for issuing norms for the ethical and safe development of AI systems.

Approach to AI Standardisation

Main features of the standardisation system

China's standardisation system is centrally coordinated by the government and organised across different levels: national, sectoral, local, industry association, and individual organisation-level.

At the national level, the SAC is responsible for all activities related to standards development. SAC sits within the State Administration of Market Regulation (SAMR), a regulatory agency under the authority of China's State Council, and is responsible for delivering national standards plans, approving and publishing cross-sectoral national standards, guiding and supervising sub-national standardisation work, and representing China in international standards bodies.

²⁴ Standing Committee of the Shenzhen Municipal People's Congress, [Regulations for the Promotion of the Artificial Intelligence Industry in Shenzhen Special Economic Zone](#) 《深圳经济特区人工智能产业促进条例》, 2022.

In the absence of national standards, technical requirements for specific industrial sectors can be specified by relevant ministries. If both national and sectoral standards are missing, or if stricter technical requirements are needed, local standards can be developed at the provincial and municipal levels. Finally, standards can also be developed by industry associations or companies. The different standardisation levels are organised hierarchically—lower-level standards must comply with higher-level ones and can only be stricter than the latter.

The Chinese government is actively involved in setting the nation's overall standardisation agenda, as well as developing and approving standards. The State Council plans major standardisation reforms and policies, and coordinates the development of cross-sectoral standards. It is also directly involved in national standardisation efforts through the SAC and oversees ministries and subnational administrations responsible for developing sectoral and local standards. This extends to industry association standards being developed under the guidance and supervision of relevant administrative departments.

The Chinese government uses standards to regulate the country's internal market, particularly on issues of product quality, consumer safety, and IP protection. In addition, standards also work as important tools to promote scientific and technological progress, ensure national security, and foster economic and social development.

China's national standards body, the SAC, has a legal obligation to ensure that the technical committees and expert groups responsible for developing standards are broadly representative of different stakeholders. Technical committees are composed of government representatives, industry associations, individual companies—both Chinese and international—and academic researchers. Civil society organisations are not usually mentioned in standardisation policies, and information about their involvement in standardisation work is not readily available.

Standards can play different roles in the Chinese legal system. At the national level, standards can be either mandatory or voluntary. Mandatory standards have the force of law and are used to regulate specific issues concerning the protection of human health, safety, and intellectual property. Non-mandatory national standards are simply considered 'recommended', as are all sub-national standards. Often, however, voluntary standards are cited or recommended in regulations, thus assuming the status of de facto requirements.

Compared with other major jurisdictions, China's standardisation system stands out for the degree of direct government involvement in standards development; the explicit use of quantitative targets to drive standardisation output both nationally and internationally; and the hierarchical relationship between different levels of standards. These features have implications for how standards are developed, adopted, and enforced in practice.

National AI-focused standardisation activities

AI standardisation in China is driven by the China Electronics Standardisation Institute (CESI), a think tank controlled by the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology (MIIT) and tasked with advancing standardisation objectives set by China's National AI Standardisation Group. CESI does not have the power to adopt standards but can organise technical committees and discussion groups to guide the development of standards that will then be adopted by MIIT in the form of sector-level standards. Overall, the Chinese AI standards ecosystem is relatively advanced compared to other countries. As of June 2026, more than 50 national AI standards have already been published, and several more are under development.²⁵

The national AI standardisation agenda was first formalised in July 2020, when five central authorities issued the *Guidelines for the Construction of a National New*

²⁵ [National Public Service Platform for Standards Information](#), accessed 21/06/2026.

Generation Artificial Intelligence Standard System.²⁶ These initial guidelines established a foundational framework with phased objectives for 2021 and 2023. Following a public consultation, an updated version was published in June 2024.²⁷ This latest iteration set ambitious targets for 2026—including the development of over 50 national and industry standards, adoption by more than 1,000 enterprises, and participation in at least 20 international standard projects—while reorganising the national AI standard system into seven core domains:

- Foundational common standards.
- Foundational support.
- Key technologies.
- Intelligent products and services.
- Empowerment of new industrialisation.
- Industry applications.
- Safety/governance.

Interestingly, while the 2020 guide referred to ‘safety/ethics’ as a cross-cutting category helpful to comply with standards under the core domains, the 2024 edition reframed the same category as ‘safety/governance’ and defined it as a standalone, structural domain of national standardisation activities. This shift formalised a broader understanding of AI standardisation as an important governance mechanism.

In February 2024, SAC’s Technical Committee 260 on Cybersecurity (SAC/TC260) published the first Chinese standard on generative AI: *Basic Safety Requirements for Generative Artificial Intelligence Services*.²⁸ The standard aims to support the

²⁶ Standards Administration of China, [Guidelines for the Construction of a National New Generation Artificial Intelligence Standard System](#) 《国家新一代人工智能标准体系建设指南》, 2020.

²⁷ Ministry of Industry and Information Technology publicly, [Guidelines for the Construction of a Comprehensive Standardisation System for the National Artificial Intelligence Industry](#) 《国家人工智能产业综合标准化体系建设指南》, 2024.

²⁸ SAC/TC260, [Basic Safety Requirements for Generative Artificial Intelligence Services \(English translation\)](#) 《全国网络安全标准化技术委员会技术文件：生成式人工智能服务安全基本要求》, 2024.

implementation of the *Interim Administrative Measures for Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) Services* and lays out safety requirements for Chinese providers of generative artificial intelligence services. These include measures on collecting, annotating and inspecting data used to train foundation models, ensuring the accuracy and safety of the content generated by such models, updating and upgrading AI models, protecting IP rights, and managing safety risks across the supply chain. The standard also includes an annex with a list of more than 30 risks common to generative AI applications, such as unfair outcomes, disclosure of personally identifiable information, and copyright infringement.

In September 2024, SAC/TC260 also published the *AI Safety Governance Framework*.²⁹ The framework is not a formal standard and offers general safety guidance for AI developers, service providers, and users. It outlines high-level governance principles, describes some of the most common AI risks, and highlights good practices to address them.

In December 2024, the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology established a Technical Committee for AI standardisation responsible for formulating and revising AI standards. Before the establishment of such a committee, AI standardisation fell under the remit of multiple technical committees—primarily TC28 (Information Technology), TC260 (Cybersecurity), and TC124 (Electronic Measurement Instruments). This signalled the government’s move from treating AI standardisation as a subset of broader ICT standardisation toward recognising it as a distinct, cross-cutting domain.

Engagement in international AI standardisation

²⁹ SAC/TC260, [AI Safety Governance Framework](#) 《人工智能安全治理框架》, 2024.

Though the Chinese administration historically focused on developing its own standards instead of aligning with the international standardisation system, over the past decade it has increasingly aimed to engage with and contribute to international standard development processes. In fact, the Chinese government increasingly sees international standardisation as a means of expanding its international influence. With this in mind, the government is not only increasing its participation in international standardisation bodies, but also explicitly aims to lead strategic standardisation projects. These aspirations are reflected in a set of quantitative indicators that the government has developed to measure its influence in international SDOs. These include the number of Chinese chairs, registered experts, secretaries, and other representatives in international SDOs, the number of international standards adopted domestically, and the number of international meetings held in China.³⁰ China's performance appears to be improving across most of these indicators.³¹

Conclusion

Overall, China's AI governance trajectory shows a dense and fast-developing set of application-specific regulations introduced through departmental rules, interim measures and other administrative regulatory instruments. One of the main advantages of this approach is its agility. Departmental rules allow regulators to issue targeted and technically specific requirements more quickly compared to developing and enforcing national laws. This is visible in China's measures on algorithmic recommendation, deep synthesis technology, generative AI services, and anthropomorphic AI interaction services, many of which are issued jointly by several competent departments and framed around 'inclusive and prudent' governance.

China's approach can be understood as incremental and adaptive: administrative regulation develops first in specific application areas, while a broader and higher-level

³⁰ Chinese Communist Party Central Committee and State Council, [National Standardization Development Outline \(English Translation\)](#) 《国家标准化发展纲要》, 2021.

³¹ Center for Intelligence Research and Analysis, [A New "Great Game?": China's Role in International Standards for Emerging Technologies](#), 2022.

legislative framework remains in progress. However, this approach also has limits. Departmental rules sit below laws and administrative regulations in China's legal hierarchy. They must remain consistent with higher-level legal norms and cannot, without a proper legal basis, reduce the rights of citizens, legal persons or other organisations, increase their obligations, expand departmental powers, or reduce statutory duties.

Pull out quote example: has emerged as one of the largest AI economies as well as an early mover in AI regulation. As part of its declared ambition to become a global leader in AI innovation by 2030, the Chinese government is developing a comprehensive regulatory framework.